

Effect of Muscle Energy Technique along with Segmental Stabilization Exercise on Pain, Range of Motion and Function in Subjects with Chronic Mechanical Low Back Pain A Randomized Clinical Trial

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ABSTRACT

Background & purpose: Mechanical low back pain most commonly occurs due to prolonged sitting or forward bending. Muscle Energy Technique (MET) and Segmental Stabilization Exercise (SSE) are one of those Physiotherapeutic techniques which can be used in clinical set up to relieve the symptoms of mechanical low back pain. The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of muscle energy technique along with segmental stabilization exercise on chronic mechanical low back pain.

Subjects and methods: Thirty four (n = 34) subjects were randomly assigned into 2 groups. Subjects in Group-A (n=17) were treated by muscle energy technique (MET) along with segmental stabilization exercise (SSE), moist hot pack and subjects in Group-B (n=17) were treated by segmental stabilization exercise and moist hot pack. Numerical pain rating scale (NPRS), Modified-modified Schobers test (MMST) and Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) was measured at pre and post intervention level.

Result: Data analysis revealed statistical significant improvement after 10 sessions of intervention in all outcome parameters. But between group comparison showed non-significant result for active flexion range of motion of lumbar spine (p value >0.05).

Conclusion: This study revealed that MET with SSE has a significant effect in improving pain and functional status. However, they do not have significant effect on lumbar spine flexion ROM in subjects with chronic mechanical low back pain.

Keywords: MET, SSE, MMST, NPRS, ODI.

INTRODUCTION

Low back pain (LBP) is characterized by slowly or suddenly occurring pain with or without radiation to the buttock or down the lower leg which may or may not be associated with concomitant restriction in range of motion. ^[1] LBP is the second most common reason for absenteeism from work and a more frequent use of health services and work leave entitlements. ^[2] It is estimated that 70-80% of adults may have an episode low back pain at least once in their lifetime. ^[3] Low back pain is one of the most common musculoskeletal conditions worldwide, with a lifetime prevalence of 80-85%. ^[4] LBP pain that is exacerbated by mechanical movements (e.g. prolonged sitting or forward bending) is usually predominantly nociceptive in nature, is referred as mechanical low back pain (MLBP). Mechanical low back pain varies with physical activities (e.g. prolonged sitting or forward bending) and with time. ^[5] Only 15% of low back pain has an identifiable cause while the rest of the 85% is non-specific low back pain. ^[6] The characteristic features of the mechanical low back pain are ache, tension or stiffness in the back, weakness of core muscles. The pain over the low back region can be triggered by sitting in poor posture, not maintaining proper ergonomics during work or incorrect lifting of heavy weight. ^[7]

When a healthy subject begins to bend forward the erector spinae (ES) muscle contracts powerfully to control the movement and then suddenly relax completely to achieve full flexion. In mechanical low back pain erector spinae fails to relax completely during flexion, this leads to failure in achieving the full spinal flexion range of motion. Each vertebra needs stiffness and stability to work effectively to reduce degeneration of joint structures. ^[8] The core serves as the muscular corset that works as a unit to stabilize the body and the spine with or without limb movement. Transversus Abdominis (TrA) provides support for the abdominal wall and has vital role in maintenance of posture, allows for trunk movement (flexion, extension, lateral flexion) and also responsible for raising intra-abdominal pressure. Lumbar Multifidus (LM) provides a stiffening effect on the lumbar spine through its attachment to the thoracolumbar fascia and works to provide joint stabilization at each segmental level. Poor core muscles stability increases the stress along with the risk of injury to supporting structures of spine and develops low back pain. ^[9]

There are several treatment approaches for low back pain which includes: patient education, lifestyle modification, medication, electro-physical agents, exercises etc. ^[1] Various physiotherapeutic measures are available to treat chronic mechanical low back pain such as therapeutic modalities, exercise involving neuromuscular re-education, resistance training and manual therapy (myofascial release, muscle energy technique (MET) and strain-counter strain technique etc.). ^[10] Muscle energy technique (MET) is a versatile technique traditionally used to address muscular pain, joint dysfunction, improve range of motion (ROM) and increase strength of muscle. ^[11] Muscle energy technique such as post isometric relaxation stretch has been used to lengthen a shortened or contracted muscle. ^[12] According to current evidence-based clinical guidelines, the mechanical low back pain is treated with training on specific muscles of the lumbar spine such as LM and TrA. ^[13] These muscles are involved on segmental stabilization exercise (SSE) by using isometric co-contraction of muscles. SSE aim to restore the stability of the trunk and the motor control of deep trunk muscles. ^[14]

There are so many literature evidences which show the effect of muscle energy technique and there are also sufficient evidences which show the beneficial effects of segmental stabilization exercise in subjects with chronic mechanical low back pain. But there

are very few literature evidences which compare the effect of muscle energy technique along with segmental stabilization exercise and segmental stabilization exercise alone in subjects with chronic mechanical low back pain. Therefore this study was designed to determine the effect of the Muscle energy technique (MET) along with segmental stabilization exercise (SSE) and segmental stabilization exercises alone on pain, range of motion and function in subjects with chronic mechanical low back pain.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was performed at National Institute for Locomotor Disabilities (Divyangjan), Kolkata, India. Approval of Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC) was taken before commencement of the study. The subjects of age group between 20-45 (both male and female population) with complaint of low back pain from previous three months and having pain intensity at NPRS between 3 to 8 were included in this study. Subjects with low back pain with unilateral/bilateral radiations (e.g. sciatica, disc herniation, canal stenosis), lower limb and spinal structural deformity (scoliosis, spondylolisthesis etc), fracture of lumbar spine or pelvis, any history of spinal surgery (e.g. laminectomy, discectomy), infectious disease of spine (TB), Ankylosing Spondylitis, Rheumatoid arthritis, Transverse myelitis, Pre-diagnosed cardio respiratory diseases or neurological disorders (stroke, SCI etc), red flag sign including thoracic pain, previous history of carcinoma, tumor and steroid injection (in last 3 month), psychiatric disorders or unco-operative subjects were excluded from this study.

70 subjects with chronic MLBP were approached with proposal of this study. Out of 70 subjects 19 subjects were excluded and 10 subjects were not willing to participate. 41 subjects who met the inclusion criteria were explained in detail in their preferred language about the study. Written informed consent in their preferred language was taken from subjects who agreed to participate. The subjects were randomly allocated into two groups by cheat picking method. Subjects in Group A (n=20) were treated by Muscle Energy Technique along with Segmental Stabilization Exercise. Subjects in Group B (n=21) were treated by Segmental Stabilization Exercise alone. Seven (07) subjects (Group-A=03; Group-B=04) were dropped out from this study and were excluded from analysis as shown in consort flow diagram (Figure-01).

Outcome Measures:

Pain intensity after activity was measured by Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), active spinal flexion range of motion by Modified Modified Schobers Test (MMST) and functional status was measured by Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) at pre-intervention and after 10 sessions (5 sessions per week for 2 weeks) of intervention.

The 11-point NPRS was used to assess the subject's self-reporting pain intensity after activity. The NPRS was administered verbally or graphically for self completion. The subjects were asked to indicate the numeric value from 0-10 points on the segmented scale which best described their pain intensity. Higher score indicated greater pain intensity.^[15]

To measure the active Spinal flexion ROM by MMST, the subject stood erect; arms at side, with feet placed apart on the floor. The therapist stood behind the subject and identified the posterior superior iliac spines (PSIS) by marking the PSIS of both sides. Then a body mark on the midline of the spine horizontal to PSIS was made and another mark on the spinous process 15 cm superior to the PSIS line was made. Then the subject was instructed to bend forward as far as they can (within pain free range) while keeping their knee straight. After reaching forward bent position, the new distance between the superior and inferior skin marking was measured again.^[16] Oswestry Disability Index is an extremely important tool used by researcher to measure a subject's functional disability with low back pain. The test is considered the 'gold standard' of low back functional outcome tools. The ODI is comprised of 10 items related to ADL like walking, standing, sitting, sleeping, lifting, etc. with associated statements for the subject to select their ability to manage their everyday life while dealing with pain. Each 10 items in the ODI has 6 statements from which the patients were requested to select one.^[17] For each section total possible score was 5. The points obtained were added in each section and the level of disability was calculated by the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Subject Score}}{\text{Number of sections completed} \times 5} \times 100 = \% \text{ of disability}$$

INTERVENTIONS:

All subjects in Group-A and Group-B had received moist hot packs (MHP) over the paraspinal area for 15 minutes prior to exercise and home exercise program were demonstrated to all of them by the primary investigator.^{[18][19]} All the subjects in Group-A were treated with Muscle energy technique along with segmental stabilization exercise. Muscle energy technique was performed in the form of post-isometric relaxation technique for erector spinae muscle. The contraction was held for 7-10 seconds and relaxed for 2-3 seconds. Appropriate breathing instructions were given. After that, on exhalation, the trunk was taken very slightly beyond the restriction barrier and was held there for 10-30 seconds.^[20]

All subjects in Group-B were treated by segmental stabilization exercise. SSE of Transversus Abdominis (TrA) and Lumbar Multifidus (L.M) muscle was taught to the subject by using pressure biofeedback unit (PBU). Details of SSE and its progression were given in Table-01.^[21] These procedures were repeated 3 times per session for 10 sessions (5 sessions per week for 2 weeks). Ergonomic advice was explained to all the subjects in Group-A and Group-B.^[22]

Statistical Analysis:

Statistical analysis was performed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 28. In demographic data, nominal level of data was analysed by non-parametric test using Chi Square Test; ordinal, interval or ratio level of data was analysed by parametric test using Independent Sample T test. For outcome measures, within group difference were analysed by using Paired Sample T-test and between group differences were analysed by using Independent Sample T Test. The tests were applied at 95% confidence interval with α value set at 0.05. For level of significance P value was set to below 0.05 to be considered as significant difference.

RESULTS:

The age and gender distribution and pre-intervention data of all outcome parameters (n=34) in both the groups were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$) which was indicative of the homogeneous nature of the data (Table-02). Intra-group comparison revealed significant statistical difference ($p < 0.05$) in respect to pain intensity (NPRS), active flexion range of motion of lumbar spine (MMST) and functional status (ODI) in both Group-A and Group-B (Table-03). In inter-group comparison, Group-A showed significant improvement than Group-B in respect to pain intensity (NPRS) and functional status (ODI) (p value < 0.05), but non-significant difference was found between the groups for active flexion range of motion of lumbar spine (MMST) (p value > 0.05) after 10 sessions of intervention (Table-03).

DISCUSSION:

This study was aimed to find the effect of muscle energy technique along with segmental stabilization exercise and segmental stabilization exercise alone on pain, range of motion and function in subjects with chronic mechanical low back pain. Both the groups showed significant improvement in pain intensity, active spinal flexion ROM and functional status after 10 sessions of treatment. This study showed that subjects in Group-A had more significant improvement in respect to pain intensity and functional status than Group-B after 10 sessions of treatment. But non-significant difference was found in active spinal flexion ROM in Group-A as compared to Group-B after 10 sessions of treatment.

Failure of relaxation of erector spinae muscle during lumbar flexion (Flexion Relaxation Phenomenon) may lead to abnormal strain to erector spinae muscle which causes development of low back pain. [23] MET of erector spinae muscle was performed by using post isometric relaxation (PIR) procedure which may stimulate the stretch receptors of Golgi Tendon Organ (GTO) of erector spinae muscle after the isometric contraction that resulted in activation of both muscle and joint mechanoreceptors. [24] This leads to sympathetic excitation of nociceptive large diameter afferent fiber and resulted in activation of the periaqueductal gray (PAG) which plays an important role in descending modulation of pain by sending the inhibitory stimulus to dorsal horn of the spinal cord. Thus effectively closes the spinal gate to the cerebral cortex and decreases the sensation of pain. This mechanism is known as 'Pain gate control theory'. [25] This study supports the findings of El-Bandrawy A.M et al (2014), who concluded that Muscle energy technique is an effective and safe method in alleviating postnatal low back pain because MET may help in repositioning a dysfunctional joint and treat the affected muscle along with voluntary isometric contraction of MET may improve the neuromuscular control and reduce the low back pain. [18]

By using pressure biofeedback unit, low load exercises of transversus abdominis and lumbar multifidus may help in restoring the recruitment order of core muscle. That may result in generation of muscle response pattern to activate and promote the co-ordinate action of the spinal muscles, provide mechanical stability and improve recruitment order. Thus in turn SSE helped in reducing the compressive load on spine which might have lead to reduction of pain intensity. [19] According Hodges (1999) and Morris et al (1961), the activation of TrA may develop rise in intra abdominal pressure within the abdominal cavity which creates a distraction of the lumbar spine which may result in decrease in the compressive load on it and so pain decreases. [26]

When PIR was given to agonist muscle i.e. to the erector spinae muscle, it may cause increase in extensibility of agonist muscle by inducing 'reflex relaxation' of that muscle caused by presynaptic inhibition and 'autogenic inhibition' of Golgi tendon organ which inhibit the activation of alpha motor neuron. [27] Also in MET muscle was taken into extreme lengthened position which may lead to increase in myofascial tissue extensibility that may be due to viscoelastic phenomenon. [28] The Golgi tendon inhibitory reflex is activated by isometric contraction and relaxation of the muscle may be induced by passive lengthening of that muscle, thus MET can decrease the overall stiffness and increase in flexion ROM of lumbar spine. [29] This study supports the findings of Sewani R. et al (2017), who concluded that MET not only increases ROM of joints but also increases extensibility of muscle by means of a mechanism expressed as "increased tolerance to stretch". [30]

Weakened muscles may cause mechanical irritation to pain sensitive structures which may be responsible for reduction of lumbar flexion ROM. The contraction of TrA and LM in SSE that may strengthen the deep trunk muscle, induce normal joint loading and enhance lumbar stability by maintaining spinal balance. [31] Bhadauria E. et al (2017) concluded that the lumbar stabilization group proved to be more effective form of exercise on improving lumbar flexion ROM than the dynamic strengthening groups, and the Pilates group due to improvement of strength and endurance of deep trunk muscles and also improve the control and co-ordination of deep trunk muscles. [32]

In MET of erector spinae muscle, passive lengthening followed by isometric contraction may help in improving proprioceptive feedback and recruitment of motor units in erector spinae muscle. This leads to improvement of pain and flexion ROM of lumbar spine in subject with LBP. Thus MET of erector spinae muscle reduces the functional limitation of life. [33]

While training the deep trunk muscles with SSE improves the activation of motor control mechanism and improvement of coordination of trunk muscles. [34] Thus SSE improves ROM of lumbar spine and reduces pain around the low back area. This results in improvement of quality of life and reduces the functional limitation. Kapetanovic A. et al (2016) concluded that segmental stabilization exercise was an effective method in improving pain and functional disability due to restoration of the motor control of deep trunk muscle and reduction of pain may improve the functional disability. [35]

So, in this study MET along with SSE was more effective in reduction of pain and improvement of functional status than SSE alone in subjects with chronic mechanical low back pain. But MET along with SSE could not effectively increase lumbar spine flexion ROM as compared to SSE alone.

CONCLUSION: The result of this study showed that MET along with segmental stabilization exercise had a significant effect in improving pain and functional status as compared to segmental stabilization exercise alone but MET along with segmental stabilization exercise does not have significant effect on lumbar spine flexion ROM as compared to segmental stabilization exercise alone in subjects with Chronic Mechanical low back pain.

LIMITATIONS: This study has small sample size and short period of intervention. No follow up was included in data analysis. The therapist was not blinded so it was single blinded and true control group was absent in this study. It was a single centre study.

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Figure 01: Consort Flow Diagram

Table-01: SEGMENTAL STABILIZATION EXERCISE

EXERCISE	
I.	Local Segmental Stabilization Exercise with PBU for TrA
II.	Local Segmental Stabilization Exercise with PBU for L.M.
III.	Closed Chain Segmental Control (CCSC) with PBU
IV.	Open Chain Segmental Control (OCSC) with PBU And Progression Into Function

TABLE-02: DEMOGRAPHIC AND PRE-INTERVENTION DATA

	Group-A (n=17) (Mean± SD)	Group-B (n=17) (Mean± SD)	t-Value	P-Value
Age	32.00 ± 8.75	32.35 ± 7.25	-0.12	0.89
Male/Female	06/11	10/07	(χ^2 -value) 1.88	0.16
NPRS ₀	06.11 ± 0.85	06.70 ± 0.91	-1.92	0.063
MMST ₀	05.33 ± 0.87	05.38 ± 0.79	-0.16	0.871
ODI ₀	52.06 ± 7.94	54.06 ± 9.25	-0.67	0.504

Table-03: INTRA-GROUP & INTER-GROUP COMPARISON

	Group-A (n=17)			Group-B (n=17)			INTER-GROUP
	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention	p-Value	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention	p-Value	p-Value
NPRS	06.11 ± 0.85	01.88 ± 1.36	0	06.70 ± 0.91	03.41 ± 1.58	0	0.005
MMST	05.33 ± 0.87	06.41 ± 0.73	0	05.38 ± 0.79	06.41 ± 0.83	0	1.00
ODI	52.06 ± 7.94	27.24 ± 5.44	0	54.06 ± 9.25	33.94 ± 8.62	0	0.01

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